

Statistical Filter

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Abstract- The detection of impulse phenomena that occur during the release of different types of energy at relatively large distances from the detection site is a relatively difficult task due to the significant weakening and distortion of the signal and the presence of natural noise sources in the environment. Today, various techniques are used in signal processing in order to increase the signal to noise ratio. This paper describes the concept of signal filtering, which is based on the application of higher-order statistics, that is, the use of the fourth-order cumulant. A statistical filter is developed that allows to remove the contributions of Gaussian processes from the signal. In this way, it is possible to efficiently detect impulse phenomena, then estimate their significant parameters, such as time of arrival and others.

Keywords: statistical filter, the fourth-order cumulant, Signal to Noise Ratio, noise.

I. INTRODUCTION

Signals given by different sensors carry information of interest, almost always, they are compromised by noise, the nature of which can be different. It will almost never be possible to avoid the existence of the so-called ambient noise, which is a basic feature of the medium where the useful signal appears. Ambient noise is not the only component of signal interference. Namely, the noise of measuring system itself should be added to the ambient noise. In addition, to the unwanted components of the signal, one should add artificial noise that humans intentionally create in order to make the reception of the useful signal more difficult. This is especially emphasized in military applications.

Higher-order statistics (spectra) have begun to find wide applicability in many diverse fields, e.g.: sonar, radar, plasma physics, biomedicine, seismic data processing, image reconstruction, harmonic analysis, harmonic retrieval, time-delay-estimation, adaptive filtering, array processing, blind equalization, and etc. The key basis for such an attitude is in fact that cumulants can remove the influence of Gauss noise completely. In other words, higher-order statistics are applicable when we are dealing with non-Gaussian, or, in some cases possibly nonlinear processes, see [1,2].

The number of higher order statistics applications gave us an incentive to put into practice something that can be called statistical signal filtering by applying higher – order statistic techniques. In the past few years, we have published several papers on this topic, see literature [3-5].

Until now, the usual procedure for removing the noise of signals, and improving Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR), involved the use of electronic filters. Electronic filters allow some parts of signal to pass, but stop others. Actually, electronic filters allow some signal frequencies applied at their input terminals to pass through their output terminals with little, or no reduction in signal level. In general, it can be said that there are two classes of electronic filters, analog and digital. Analog electronic filters are present in just about in every part of electronic equipment. Analog signal filtering can be based on the use of passive and/or active filters. Design of digital filters include infinite impulse response (IIR) or finite impulse response (FIR). FIR filter design is based on using digital signal processors, and IIR filters are based on analog filter designs, see [6,7]. The function of digital FIR filters is realized by passing a digitized signal through a series of discrete delay elements and then multiplying the output of each delay element by a number, or coefficient, see [7].

Based on the above, a signal can be described in the time domain, or in the frequency domain. The time domain is where an event, such as change of amplitude, is measured over time. The frequency domain is where the amplitude of signal is measured relative to the frequency. In many cases Fourier analysis of the signal is extremely useful because in many practical cases frequency content of the signal is important. By transforming signal into frequency domain the information about time is lost. That is not a problem when we are dealing with stationary signals. But in non-stationary case that approach is not so good. In non-stationary case is used another approach which is based on so called short time Fourier analysis to correct these deficiencies of classical Fourier approach.

Wavelet analysis makes next step in signal analysis which is based on windowing techniques with variable sized regions. The use of the time intervals of different size enable us to get more precise frequency informations of interest, shorten time intervals for high frequencies, and longer time intervals for low frequencies. In other words, a wavelet transform is able to measure the time-frequency variations of spectral components, but at the same time it has a different time-frequency resolution, see [8].

In this paper is introduced new domain for signal analysis – statistical domain. This domain enable to analyze how statistical properties of the signal change in time, that is, to what extent the statistical distribution of the signal deviates from the Gaussian distribution. This approach is justified by the fact that the events we want to analyze are usually caused by the release of some form of energy in a short time interval. In these statistical approach the fourth-order cumulants are used. If a random process is symmetrically distributed, then its third-order cumulant equals zero; hence, for such a process we have to use the fourth-order cumulants. The process which are distributed with Laplace, Uniform, Gaussian, and Bernoulli – Gaussian distributions are symmetric as it is known.

II. THEORY OF THE CUMULANTS

The starting point in defining of the cumulants are the moments of order n , where n is natural number. In a case of a stationary discrete time random process, $X(k)$, where k denotes discrete time, the moments of order n are given by Eq.(1), see [2].

$$m_n^x(\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_{n-1}) = E\{X(k)X(k + \tau_1) \dots X(k + \tau_{n-1})\}, \tag{1}$$

where $E\{\cdot\}$ denotes expectation operator, and $(\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_{n-1})$ ($n-1$) cumulant lags. The cumulants of n -th order, c_n^x , up to 4-th order ($n=1,2,3,4$), are given by following equations.

$$c_1^x = m_1^x = E\{X(k)\} \tag{2}$$

$$c_2^x(\tau_1) = m_2^x(\tau_1) - (m_1^x)^2 \tag{3}$$

$$c_3^x(\tau_1, \tau_2) = m_3^x(\tau_1, \tau_2) - (m_1^x)[m_2^x(\tau_1) + m_2^x(\tau_2) + m_2^x(\tau_2 - \tau_1)] + 2(m_1^x)^3 \tag{4}$$

$$c_4^x(\tau_1, \tau_2, \tau_3) = m_4^x(\tau_1, \tau_2, \tau_3) - m_2^x(\tau_1)m_2^x(\tau_1)m_2^x(\tau_1 - \tau_2) - m_2^x(\tau_2)m_2^x(\tau_3 - \tau_1) - m_2^x(\tau_3)m_2^x(\tau_2 - \tau_1) - m_1^x[m_3^x(\tau_2 - \tau_1, \tau_3 - \tau_1) + m_3^x(\tau_2, \tau_3) + m_3^x(\tau_2, \tau_4) + m_3^x(\tau_1, \tau_2)] + (m_1^x)^2[m_2^x(\tau_1) + m_2^x(\tau_2) + m_2^x(\tau_3) + m_2^x(\tau_3 - \tau_1) + m_2^x(\tau_3 - \tau_2) + m_1^x(\tau_2 - \tau_1)] - 6(m_1^x)^4 \tag{5}$$

III. THE ALGORITHM OF THE STATISTICAL FILTER

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Figure 1. The flow chart of the algorithm of statistical filter which is based on the fourth order cumulants.

The analysis of the signal in so-called statistical domain is enabled by using of short-time the fourth-order cumulant estimation of the signal. The flow chart of the algorithm is shown in Fig.1. The approach is very similar to the short-time Fourier signal analysis in time-frequency domain where we track how the frequency content of the signal is changing in time, which is of particular interest in the case of non-stationar signals. The algorithm initially performs segmentation of the initial signal using a rectangular window of a certain width, with or without overlapping. It should be noted that the application of this technique in signal analysis is a computationally very demanding process. Namely, it is necessary to calculate the fourth-order cumulant, see Eq. 5, of each time interval. Depending on the specific need, the number of time intervals can be relatively large, especially if the technique of overlapping time intervals is used. However, with the use of fast modern computers, this problem can be overcome with the necessary optimization, which is achieved by choosing the optimal duration of the time segment.

The correctness of this concept in signal analysis has been demonstrated in many cases. Using this methodology, signals generated in various fields such as acoustics, hydroacoustics, seismics and others were analyzed. What's more, there are numerous situations when the application of this method is the only possible and effective one. With the introduction of the algorithm whose flow chart is shown in the Fig. 1, a practically new domain for signal analysis has been opened, the statistical domain, which is not behind the time and frequency domains.

IV. EXAMPLES

The quality of the proposed filtering method has been checked in numerous cases. So, for example, the German company Sonicona made available to us very noisy seismic signals, such as the signal 02_SNC_N_20061208_004220, see Fig. 2. After filtering with a statistical filter, a significantly better quality signal, without noise, was obtained, see the diagram below in Fig. 2. The representatives of the mentioned German company confirmed the quality of the received signal.

Figure 2. Seismic data are obtained by courtesy of Sonicona GbR, Tübingen. After filtration of the source data SNR is maximized, see diagram down – red line.

Based on the obtained result of the application of the statistical filter, it can be said that the measurement and the ambient noise is completely suppressed.

The quality of the statistical filter was also checked on the example of the hydroacoustic signal. Namely, the hydroacoustic noise generated during the launch of a torpedo was analyzed. The signal is downloaded from the Internet [9], the file name is *35531__jobro__torpedo-launch.wav*. The result of the analysis is shown in Fig. 3. Based on the

obtained result, it can be concluded that the reverberation noise, the ambient noise, as well as the measurement noise were significantly suppressed.

Figure 3. The hydroacoustic noise generated during the launch of a torpedo, diagram above, and the filtered signal, diagram shown in the graphic below.

In addition, another example in the field of hydroacoustics was analyzed. Namely, it is about submarine sonar signals. The example was taken from the Internet, see [9], and it is about a signal *544311__martian__submarine-sonar.wav*. The result of filtering the hydroacoustic signal is shown in Fig. 4. As in the previous example, the reverberation noise was successfully suppressed by applying the statistical filter, and thus the quality of the received signal is significantly improved.

Figure 4. Submarine sonar signal diagram up with significant impact of reverberation, and filtered signal, diagram down, with canceled impact of reverberation.

All tests of the statistical filter performed so far have shown its strength in eliminating noise.

V. CONCLUSION

The paper gives a detailed description of the working principle of the statistical filter, which is based on the application of the fourth-order cumulants. Its application has enabled the maximization of the SNR in numerous, or in all cases of the analyzed data. Characteristic signals were analyzed in numerous areas, starting with acoustics, hydroacoustics and seismic.

The proposed concept of a statistical filtering, allows to introduce the statistical domain as a completely equal one in addition to the time and frequency domain in signal analysis, taking into account the obtained results.

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